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Effect of Concept Mapping on Biology Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of concept mapping on Biology students' academic performance in secondary schools in Etche ethnic nationality of Rivers State. To achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher formulated four objectives of the study, four research questions and four null hypotheses that guided the study. The research design used was quasi-experimental design. The population of this study comprises of total number of 11,113 Senior Secondary school students In Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State. A sample size of 241 SS1 students were used for the study. The researcher applied purposive sampling techniques in determining the sample size. The instrument used for this study was Biology Performance Test (BPT). The data gathered were analyzed using statistical tools of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the data analysis, the findings of the study revealed that concept mapping strategy has positive and significant effect on students' academic performance taught biology and that male students relatively obtained higher mean scores than the female students when taught with concept mapping strategy. Based on findings, the researcher recommends that- government, through the senior secondary school management should adopt concept mapping instructional strategy instead of lecture method in teaching of Biology and the secondary school management should organize awareness and enlightenment campaign for teachers to know importance of concept mapping strategy.

Keywords: Effect, Concept, Mapping, Biology Students, Academic Performance,

INTRODUCTION

Education has been described as a vital and indispensable key to any form of development. It is an instrument for economic, political and scientific development of all nations. Dabah (2016) defined Science Education as the study of the connection between science as a discipline and the application of educational principles to comprehend science teaching and learning in the classroom. Therefore, science education acquaints students with certain basic knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for future work in science and science-related fields. According to Onwu (2020) science teachers are expected to make the science subjects more relevant, enjoyable, easy and meaningful to students. Teaching methods need to be improved and appropriate teaching strategies employed as the teaching-learning situation may demand. This could be the reason why the Federal Government of Nigeria emphasised on the teaching of science (biology belong) in its National Policy on Education (FGN, 2008).

Teaching method is seen as one comprising the principles and methods applied by the teachers to promote students learning, and these strategies are determined partly on the subject matter to be

taught and partly by the nature of the learner. According to Sakala (2013), which method is best for a particular lesson is determined by a number of factors, including the students' age and developmental level, what they already know and what they need to know, the subject-matter content, the lesson's objective, and the time, space, and material resources available.

Concept mapping method is an instructional strategy for teaching the learners using the instructional materials in order to enable the learners to acquire skills necessary for performing the given task. Concept mapping involves showing by reason or proof, explaining or making clear by use of examples or experiments. Put more simply, Concept mapping means 'to clearly show'. In teaching through Concept mapping, students are set up to potentially conceptualize class material more effectively. Concept Mapping is the process of seeking out related concepts, ideas and sub-concepts for a particular topic; and linking them up with lines on which are inscribed possible propositions that can define their relation; and laying them out carefully to bring out ones understanding graphically.

Biology is regarded as one of the important science subjects studied in Nigerian senior secondary schools. Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) confirms the importance of biology in Nigerian educational curriculum by enlisting it as one of the core science subjects in external examinations. Therefore, biology is an essential and somehow compulsory science subject studied in the Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria. To science inclined students, biology is a core subject, but to arts inclined, it is a choice to fulfil all righteousness. Martins-Omole and Yusuf (2013) posited that biology occupies a unique position in the school curriculum as it is central to many sciences related professional courses in higher institutions such as Microbiology, Medicine, Pharmacy, Nursing, Dentistry and other related courses. It, therefore, becomes imperative that anyone who wishes to undergo the above mentioned courses in higher institution is expected to offer biology as a pre-requisite subject to enable him/her gain admission into higher institution. However, the students low performance in biology in the external examinations has been a source of worry to teachers, parents and other stakeholders.

Gender is the societal meaning assigned to male and female with a particular role that each should play. In other words, it is the role and responsibility of male and female that is created in families, societies and culture. The concept of gender is the expectation shield about the characteristics, attitudes, and likely behaviours of both men and women in the society. Gender is one amongst the foremost fascinating and actively debated variables in academic analysis, however with conflicting results. According to them, gender differentiation that exist in some science related subjects which lead to variation in academic performance of male and female students remain an issue of concern to researchers. Moyer, Hackett and Everett in Ajaja (2015) indicated that the contemporary students are learning science in the passive way in classroom where information is organized and presented to them by their teachers. To what extent this lecture method of instruction assists the students is also a major concern to many scholars.

Lecture method is just one of the several teaching methods, and stands to be the oldest and widely used method of instruction in classrooms. It is a long tradition, probably even dating from the dawn of mankind. Lecturing is a time-tested instructional method where an instructor who has the knowledge on a given subject matter delivers all relevant information to learners verbally. It relies on one-way communication that mostly leaves the learners as passive participants only to take notes and probably ask questions after the delivery, if and when time permits. According to Schmidt (2017) lectures can be quite engaging if delivered by a charismatic teacher who has the ability to explain difficult concepts in a simple yet effective way. However, Kelly (2018) noted that lecturing is ultimately an out-dated form of instructional delivery that does not benefit students in that it does not accommodate individual needs but cause students to rely on the teachers.

Concept mapping method of instruction or learning is one of the currently evolved innovative methods of science instruction. It is process-focused and learner-centred, as well as a meta-learning technique that is based on theory of meaningful learning (Kelly, 2019). It is a special two-dimensional diagrammatic learning which emphasizes the relationship between and among important concepts. However, some researchers have noted that concept mapping has its own disadvantages. It is not beneficial to low ability learners. Many science teachers lack the knowledge and so no skills and competence required for effective use of the method. The method requires close guidance and supervision of the learners which is often not possible with large classes. It may be expensive in terms

of resources for its application. Often times the important concepts and links are omitted and it may not be suitable for certain science concepts. Although instructions often use concept maps to promote learning, these visuals have the potential disadvantage if they muddle relationships and discourage critical thinking.

Concept of Biology

Biology, as defined by Ogunleye (2022), is the study of life. It is a mandatory subject offered in all senior secondary schools in Nigeria, catering to both science and arts-oriented students. Odogwu (2018) emphasized the significance of teaching biology as it enables students to understand the world around them and equips them with essential skills to contribute to the advancement of society. Furthermore, Odogwu (2018) noted that biology serves as a foundation for teaching students how to apply scientific concepts and principles to address everyday challenges.

Biology remains one of the basic sciences whose teaching and learning is universally known to be efficient and successful, if only undertaken simultaneously with the help of adequate instructional resources and facilities. Biology plays a vital role in the field of biochemistry, medicine, physiology, ecology, genetics, and molecular biology and as such, biology has been made a central focus in most human activities including being a solution to the problem of food scarcity, health, hygiene, family life, poverty eradication, management and conservation of natural resources, biotechnology, ethics, various social vices and as well lack of appropriate infrastructural materials.

Biology is one of the science subjects that senior secondary students offer in senior secondary certificate examinations in Nigeria (FRN, 2004). Interestingly, it is a popular subject among students and its popular nature among other science subjects has made it distinct choice for all students. Biology is a very important science subject and a requirement for further studies of other science related professional courses such as medicine, agriculture, pharmacy, biotechnology, genetic engineering, etc. Biology is the key to economic, intellectual, sociological, human resource development and well being of any society. It is of importance in many ways for both individual and societal development as seen in biotechnology and genetic engineering. Based on these assertions on the importance of biology, there is need for it to be properly taught in the secondary schools to improve students achievement in the subject.

Importance of Biology Teaching in Schools

It is a well-known issue today that science influences man in all aspects of life including feeding, clothing, shelter, health care, communication, transportation, space 19 exploration, as well as leisure. Ayodele, (2020) and Elechi, (2020) inferred that the most obvious effect of science has been its medical and technological applications, with the accompanying effects on health care, lifestyles, and social structures. Science also influences culture in many modern societies by playing a major role in shaping cultural world views, concepts, and thinking patterns. It is important to note that science is useful in the world today. Almost all aspects of man's life are influenced by science either directly or indirectly. Man needs to be scientifically literate to exist comfortably in his environment. This informs the need for inclusion of scientific literacy in the goals of education in Nigeria (FME, 2008). The relevance of science in development of the nation cannot be over emphasized. Scholar Ajayi, (2018), agreed that the growth of any nation to the standard of the 21st century technology should be anchored on the scientific based knowledge of her subjects. The growth of any nation is a measure of its advancement in science. Science is a major subject taught in schools all over Nigeria, and any nation that hopes to develop must not neglect the teaching of science in its schools. One of such science subjects is Biology.

Academic performance in Biology and its Impediments

Academic performance refers to a successful accomplishment or Performance in particular subject area. It is indicated by grades, marks and scores of descriptive commentaries. Academic performance also refers to how Students deal with their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers in a fixed time or academic year. Fajola (2018), used the notion of academic self-concept in referring to Individuals' knowledge and perceptions about themselves in academic performance, and convictions that they can successfully perform a given academic tasks at designated levels. 21 Fajola (2018) further stated that academic self-concept represents a more past-oriented, aggregated and relatively stable judgment about one's self-perceived ability in a particular academic domain while academic self-efficacy represents a context specific and relatively future

oriented judgment about one's confidence for successfully performing an upcoming subject-specific academic task. Rothstein (2020) argues that; learning is not only a product of formal schooling but also of communities, families and peers. Socio-economic and socio cultural forces can affect learning and thus school achievement.

Factors Influencing Student performance in Biology

Teaching of biology as a subject in secondary schools is faced with many problems. The poor academic performance of students in biology as indicated in the report of WAEC and National Teachers Institute (NTI) as well as the result of state common entrance examination has come a persisted public outcry as regards the falling standard of biology education. Science subjects are already facing a problem. This is mostly in the area of availability of laboratories and other teaching facilities in their right number of students studying science. Biology is very important subject; it has to be given more priority. It enables one to understand himself and his intermediate environment. Nevertheless, the knowledge acquired in Biology subject is applied in many fields as Medicine, Biochemistry, Pharmacy, Microbiology and Agriculture among others. Students performance in Biology subject in Senior Secondary Certificates Examination (SSCE) has been unsatisfactory over many years. Various reasons have been attached to this problem by scholars. Dinah (2013) concluded that, availability of text books, laboratory apparatus and other learning resources contribute significantly to the performance of students in Biology examination. He added that, students with positive attitude towards the subject register better performance than those who had a negative attitude. Those with positive attitude are motivates to work hard and this is reflected in the good marks scored in the examination. Suman (2021) conducted a research on influence of parents education and parental occupation on academic performance of students. He concluded that education and occupation of parents positively influence the academic performance of children.

Meaning of Concept mapping

Ossai (2014) sees concept mapping as a graphical arrangement of key concept to show meaningful relationship among the selected concept or ideas been studied. Ajaja (2017) takes concept mapping as a learning strategy which helps students in understanding complex ideas and clarifies ambiguous relationships. Also, concept mapping may be seen as a teaching -learning strategy in which ideas that contains two or more concept are connected with other words to form a meaningful statements represented diagrammatically. It could be seen as a technique for representing the structure of information visually. Concept maps are tools for organizing and representing knowledge, they include concept which are generally enclosed in circles or boxes of some types and relationship between concept and preposition between two concepts. (Propositions are statement about some object or statement in the universe either naturally occurring or constructed.) They contain two or more concepts connected with other words to form a meaningful statement. A concept map is also a graphical representation where links (point or vertices) represent concepts and cross links (arcs or lines) represents the relationships between concepts. The links between the concepts can be one way, two ways or non-directional. The concepts and the links may be categorized and the concepts may show temporary or causal relationship between concepts. Concept map can also have been seen as a visual representation of linkages/connections between a major concept and other knowledge students has learned.

To Novak, concept map is a tool that promotes meaningful learning as opposed to rote learning. A concept map is a two dimensional representation of the relationship between key ideas. It shows us how we think and suggest affinities and association that might not otherwise be obvious. At a first glance, a concept map looks like a flow chat in which the key words are placed in boxes connected by directional arrows (Ajaja, 2017). Concept maps are excellent tools which provide instructors with diagnostic pre-assessment prior to beginning a unit and formative assessment during learning activities. Based on educational psychology theories of how we organize information, concept maps are hierarchical with broader more general items at the top and more specific topics arranged in a cascade below them. They are meta cognitive tools that empower the learner to take charge of his/her own learning in a highly and meaningful manner. According to Novak (2016), "meaningful learning involves the assimilation of new concept and proposition into cognitive structure. The most important factor influencing learning is what the learner has already known. Novaks work on concept mapping is based on the cognitive theory of David Ausubel (assimilation theory) who stresses the importance

of prior knowledge in been able to learn new concept. Concept maps have their origin in the learning movement called constructivism. Constructivists are of the view that learners construct knowledge from their existing knowledge.

The concept mapping technique was developed by Dr. Joseph D. Novak at Cornell University in the 1960s. It is based on the theories of Dr. David Ausubel, who stressed the importance of prior knowledge and a proper learning set in being able to learn about new concepts through meaningful receptive learning. The basic idea is that students are given a central concept. To that concept other related concepts that the students already know are graphically mapped. It can be done individually or in a group. It can also be done in an instructor-led setting (Martin, 2014). It is generally done at the start of a unit of activity in order to tie the new concept to already internalized ideas, but can also be done as an assessment at the end of a lesson. It is also possible for concept maps to have more than one main concept. The key is the interconnectedness of knowledge. Concept maps are highly personalized and provide an opportunity to organize course material in a way that makes most sense to you. The main point is to end up with a diagram of all of the important ideas from your class, with terms you add that describe how the ideas are connected to each other. Concept maps are a powerful tool for identifying relationships among ideas you learn in class. Understanding these relationships and depicting them visually can help you learn course material at a much deeper level and retain it better, too.

Concept maps are highly personalized and provide an opportunity to organize course material in a way that makes most sense to *you*. The main point is to end up with a diagram of all of the important ideas from your class, with terms you add that describe how the ideas are connected to each other. (Some students find that adding these linking terms is one of the most challenging part of making a concept map- actively deciding how the ideas are related is key to the effectiveness of concept maps, so don't skip the linking terms). Concept maps can be helpful learning tools in just about any class: STEM, humanities, social sciences, languages, even the arts. Similar to an outline or a flowchart, a concept map is a way of representing or organizing knowledge. However, a concept map goes beyond the typical outline in that concept maps show relationships between concepts, including bi-directional relationships. Usually, a concept map is divided into nodes and links. Nodes (often circles) represent various concepts; and links (lines) represent the relationships (propositions) between concepts.

Once completed, the concept map is a visual graphic that represents how the creator(s) thinks about a subject, topic, etc. It illustrates how knowledge is organized for the individual. In sum, "concept maps are two-dimensional representations of cognitive structures showing the hierarchies and the interconnections of concepts involved in a discipline or a sub-discipline" (Martin, 2014). Concept maps were first used by Joseph D. Novak of Cornell University in the 1960s. Concept maps have their origin in the learning movement called constructivism. Concept maps identify the way we thin, the way we see relationships between knowledge. The teacher who constructs concept maps for classes is interested in students understanding relationships between facts, not just "knowing" the facts

Concept Maps and Curriculum Design

Concept maps can be used as excellent planning devices for instruction. Edmondson, 1993, describes the importance of using concept maps to develop the curriculum for a veterinarian program: "Concept maps are effective tools for making the structure of knowledge explicit, and our hope is that by using them in our planning the material will be more accessible and more easily integrated by students". The type of curriculum described by Edmondson is based on constructivist principles. It is both problem-centered and student-centered. Instead of asking, "what do I want to teach," the emphasis is on, "what do I want students to learn?"

Martin (2014) conducted a study in which he taught education majors to use concept maps to make lesson plans. The teachers in the study found the maps quite useful for the development of course plans. "Our students view concept mapping as giving teachers a more comprehensive understanding of what they are preparing to teach, eliminating sequencing errors, and enabling teachers to develop lessons that are truly interdisciplinary".

Statement of the Problem

It is worth mentioning that the academic performance of students in the West African Senior School Certificate (WASSC) and other O'level biology external examinations has consistently been subpar.

Some authorities attribute this issue to ineffective teaching methods and various other underlying problems. This raises questions regarding the appropriateness of instructional approaches in teaching and learning biology in order to instill the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes, and retention in students, which are essential for achieving success in the subject. Previous research endeavors have been undertaken to identify suitable teaching methods that can optimize achievement in science subjects, albeit with limited success.

Biology, being a comprehensive scientific discipline within the Nigerian Educational Curriculum, holds significant importance for students of all academic inclinations, whether in the realm of sciences or arts. It is crucial to establish effective teaching and learning processes to enhance students' academic performance, particularly in external examinations, thereby facilitating their seamless transition into higher education institutions for further academic pursuits. In light of the persistent challenge at hand, the current study aims to explore the effect of concept mapping on biology students' academic performance in secondary schools in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of concept mapping on biology students' academic performance in secondary schools in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Specifically, this study sought to:

1. Investigate the academic performance of students taught Habitat using concept mapping and those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State
2. Examine the retention of students taught Habitat with concept mapping and those taught using Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State
3. Examine the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State
4. Evaluate the academic performance of Student taught Habitat using concept mapping in Urban and Rural secondary school in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions formulated by the researcher guided the study:

1. What are the academic performance of students taught Habitat using concept mapping and those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State
2. What is the difference in the retention of students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy and those taught using Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State
3. What is the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.
4. What is the academic performance of students taught Habitat using concept mapping in Urban and Rural secondary school in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Hypotheses

The following Null Hypotheses as designed by the researcher guided the study, and were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. There no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping and those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State
2. There is no significant difference in the retention of students taught Habitat using concept mapping and those taught using Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State
3. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.
4. There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Urban and Rural secondary school in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed quasi-experimental design, there are Two groups in this study; the first group is the experimental group (EG) which was exposed to Concept mapping method (X), while the second is the control group (CG) which was exposed to lecture method All the two groups were pre-tested (O1) to ensure that selected participants were not different significantly in terms of Academic Performance. The treatment and teaching periods lasted for five (5) weeks.

Immediately after the treatment, post-test (O2) was administered to the two groups to determine the effect of treatment on students Performance. The population of this study comprises a total number of 11,113 Senior Secondary school biology students in the 18 public senior secondary schools in Etche and Omuma local government area. The total number consist of 5317 male students 5,796 female students offering Biology in 18 public schools. (Source Planning Research and Statistics Rivers state senior secondary schools board (RSSSSD) 2023/2024 session). A sample size of 241 SS1 students were used for the study. The researcher applied purposive sampling technique to sample two co-educational schools in Etche and Omuma local government area of Rivers state. A total of four intact classes were drawn from the co-educational schools. Simple random sampling was used to select intact classes with more than two classes of SSI students. A total of 118 males and 123 females was used to give a sample size of 241. One intact class from each school were assigned to experimental group and the other to control group using simple random sampling. For the control group, a total of 120 students from the intact classes were used while 121 students were used for the experimental group. The instrument used for this study was Biology performance Test (BPT). The BPT used was from a composed questions by the researcher from the topic (Habitat). BPT had 30 objective test items of multiple choice question with options A, B, C and D. BPT has two sections. Section A contains name of students, sex, class and year. Section B contains 30 objective test items on the concept, Habitat. The data collected from both the experimental and control groups in the pre-test and post-test will be analyzed using the following statistical tools: the mean and standard deviation will be used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used in testing the hypotheses formulated.

RESULTS

Research Questions 1: *What is the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping and those taught Using Lecture method?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping and those taught using Lecture Method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

S/No	Group/Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Grand Mean
			Mean \bar{X}	SD	Mean \bar{X}	SD	
1.	Habitat with Concept Mapping	121	2.70	0.82	2.90	0.85	2.80
2.	Lecture Method	120	2.55	0.80	2.65	0.81	2.60

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 1 above indicates that the grand mean of 2.80 and 2.60 was achieved between concept mapping and those taught using Lecture method in their pretest and post test scores. This implies that there is positive and significant effect of concept mapping on students academic performance in Etch Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State compare to those taught using Lecture method.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference in the Retention of students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy and those taught with Lecture method?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation analysis on the difference in the Retention scores of students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy and those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

S/No	Group/method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Grand Mean
			Mean \bar{X}	SD	Mean \bar{X}	SD	
1.	Habitat using concept mapping	121	2.75	0.83	2.95	0.86	2.85
2.	Lecture Method	120	2.50	0.79	2.65	0.81	2.58

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 2 above indicates that the grand mean of 2.85 and 2.58 was achieved between the difference in the Retention of students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy and those taught with Lecture method in their pretest and post test scores. This implies that there was positive and significant difference in the Retention of students taught habitat using concept mapping strategy in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State compared to those taught with Lecture method.

Research Questions 3: *What is the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping?.*

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

S/No	Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Grand Mean
			Mean \bar{X}	SD	Mean \bar{X}	SD	
1.	Male Students	118	2.60	0.81	2.85	0.84	2.73
2.	Female Students	123	2.55	0.80	2.70	0.82	2.63

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 3 above shows that the grand mean of 2.73 and 2.63 was achieved between the academic performance of male and female students taught habitat using concept mapping in their pretest and post test scores. This implies that male students achieved higher scores than the female counterparts.

Research Question 4: *What is the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping in Urban and Rural secondary school?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard deviation analysis on the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping in Urban and Rural secondary school.

S/No	Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Grand Mean
			Mean \bar{X}	SD	Mean \bar{X}	SD	
1.	Urban secondary school	118	2.65	0.81	2.90	0.85	2.78
2.	Rural secondary school	123	2.60	0.81	2.80	0.84	2.70

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 4 above shows that the grand mean of 2.78 and 2.70 was achieved between the academic performance of students taught habitat with concept mapping in their pretest and post test scores. This implies that those in Urban secondary schools achieved higher scores than those of their Rural secondary schools counterparts.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One: There no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping and those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Table 5: ANCOVA Results of Pretest-Posttest on the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping and those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	26959.025 ^a	2	13479.513	274.952	.000	Significant
Intercept	18197.192	1	18197.192	371.182	.000	
Pretest	162.900	1	162.900	3.323	.070	
Group	26804.233	1	26804.233	176.146	.000	
Error	9657.930	227	49.025			
Total	410989.000	230				

Table 5 of the ANCOVA results reveal F-value of 176.146 and P-value of 0.000 < 0.05 (which is less than) the chosen level of significant between 1 and 227 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis 1 is **rejected**; hence the p-value < 0.05 level of significant. This indicates that there is significant difference in

the pretest and posttest on the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping and those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the retention of students taught Habitat using concept mapping and those taught using Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Table 6: ANCOVA Results of Retention of students taught Habitat using concept mapping and those taught using Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	10036.304	2	5018.152	71.158	.000	
Intercept	34230.204	1	34230.204	485.388	.000	
Pretest	73.697	1	73.697	1.045	.307	Significant
Groups	10017.101	1	10017.101	142.044	.001	
Error	42101.214	227	70.521			
Total	1168687.000	230				

Table 6 of the ANCOVA results reveal that F-value of 142.044 and P-value of $0.001 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significant between 1 and 227 degree of freedom was gotten. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 **is rejected**; hence the p-value < 0.05 level of significant. This suggests that there is significant difference on the retention of students taught Habitat using concept mapping and those taught using Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Table 7: ANCOVA Results of academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	3939.186	2	1969.593	11.874	.000	
Intercept	17177.385	1	17177.385	103.555	.000	Significant
Pretest	199.490	1	199.490	1.203	.274	
Gender	3784.394	1	3784.394	122.814	.003	
Error	32677.769	227	165.877			
Total	410989.000	200				

Table 7 of the ANCOVA results reveal F-value of 122.814 and P-value of $0.003 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significant between 1 and 227 degree of freedom was gotten. Therefore, the null hypothesis 3 **is rejected**; hence the p-value < 0.05 level of significant. This implies that there is significant difference on the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Urban and Rural secondary school in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Table 8: ANCOVA Results of Pretest-Posttest on the academic performance of Students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Urban and Rural secondary school in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	26959.025 ^a	2	13479.513	274.952	.000	Significant
Intercept	18197.192	1	18197.192	371.182	.000	
Pretest	162.900	1	162.900	3.323	.070	
Group	26804.233	1	26804.233	176.146	.000	
Error	9657.930	227	49.025			
Total	410989.000	230				

Table 8 of the ANCOVA results reveal F-value of 176.146 and P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ (which is less than) the chosen level of significant between 1 and 227 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis 4 **is rejected**; hence the p-value < 0.05 level of significant. This indicates that there is significant difference on the pretest and posttest on the academic performance of Students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy in Urban and Rural secondary school in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study in research question one: What is the academic performance of students taught with concept mapping in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State. The study reveals that the use of concept mapping strategy enhances the students academic performance when taught Habitat compared to those taught with Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State. The finding of the study is in agreement with that by Ajaja (2015) who admitted that, in teaching with Concept mapping, students are set up to potentially conceptualize class material more effectively. Kelly (2018) also noted that concept mapping involves stages and these include; brain storming stage, organizing stage, laying out stage, linking stage and finalizing the concepts.

The study in research questions two: What is the difference in the retention scores of students taught Habitat using concept mapping strategy and those taught with Lecture method indicates that use of concept mapping strategy has significant effect on the students retention when taught habitat compared to Lecture method in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State. This study is in the same view with Elechi (2020) who observed that concept mapping method is a strategy for teaching the learners using the instructional materials in order to enable the learners to acquire skills necessary for performing a given task. Concept mapping involves showing by reason or proof, explaining or making clear by use of examples or experiments. Put more simply, Concept mapping means 'to clearly show. In teaching through Concept mapping, students are set up to potentially conceptualize class material more effectively and Memory retention becomes higher when learning is done by doing and understanding.

The findings of the study in research question three: What is the academic performance of male and female students taught Habitat using concept mapping shows that male students obtains higher scores than the female students when concept mapping instructional strategy is used in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State. The finding of the study is in line with Ossia (2014) who admitted that Gender is one amongst the foremost fascinating and actively debated variables in academic analysis, however with conflicting results. Schmidt (2017) have also affirmed a significant connection between students performance and gender in biology, particularly in favour of male. It also reported that male students have higher level of academic performance in science, technology and arithmetic than their female counterparts.

The study in research questions four: What is the academic performance of students taught Habitat with concept mapping in Urban and Rural secondary school indicates that Urban secondary school students academic performance is better than the Rural secondary school students in using concept mapping strategy in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State.

This study is in the same view with Novak (2016) who observed that the concept map created by students can be used in several ways to facilitate meaningful learning. They also pointed that concept map is some kind of schematic summary of what students know. It (concept map) can be used to display students prior knowledge about a given topic or they can be used to summaries what has been learned by students after reading or completing class work. In this regard, it is often used for note taking or as a study aid. The art of map creation is a creative activity in which the learner must exert effort to clarify meanings by identifying important concepts, relationships and structure within a specified domain of knowledge and understanding, providing a kind of feedback that helps students monitor their learning and perhaps with the assistance of teachers or peers to focus attention on learning needs.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that use of concept mapping strategy enhances students academic performance taught Habitat and that male students obtains relatively

higher scores than the female students when using concept mapping strategy. The effect of concept mapping on biology students' academic performance in secondary schools in Etche Ethnic Nationality of Rivers State cannot be overemphasized due to the impact it has created in their academic performance. The study also deduced that Teaching methods such as Concept mapping, inquiry, peer-tutoring, project, problem-solving, field trips, cooperative or group learning, excursion, remedial, laboratory and guided discussion and the use of audio-visual materials have been recommended for the teaching of science. Concept maps are important to promote learning with understanding. Student participants mentioned that concept maps helped students remember concepts for a longer period and Memory retention becomes higher when learning is done by doing and understanding.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher made the following recommendations to achieve the purpose of the study.

1. Government, through the senior secondary school management should adopt concept mapping strategy instead of lecture methods in teaching of biology, because it improve the students academic performance.
2. Senior secondary school management should organize workshop, programme for teachers on how to use concept mapping instructional strategy instead of lecture method in teaching to provide them with professional development.
3. The secondary school management should organize awareness and enlightenment campaign on this innovative teaching strategy to improve the qualify of teaching in various schools
4. Curriculum developer should incorporate this strategy in curriculum guidelines for achievement of intended learning outcomes and content development for meaningful and higher order learning

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